
A Bibliometric Analysis on Indian Diaspora as seen through Web of Science Database

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ABSTRACT

Indian diaspora can be measured as the 30th state consisting of 30 million Indians living worldwide. The present quantitative study is based on data retrieved from Web of Science examines the diaspora related research of Indian community. The data analysis was done using bibliometric software, including MS Excel, VOS Viewer. The growth of publications over time and their citations are analyzed first, followed by top authors, leading institutions, international collaboration and top journals. Further, the co-occurrence of keywords and top-cited articles are analyzed. The results show that Singh S from Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology is the most productive author. At the same time, Docquier F from the Luxembourg Inst Socioecon Res is the most influential amongst all authors and the University of Kwazulu Natal and University Of London is the most productive institution.

1. Introduction:

1.1 Diaspora

The term diaspora has originated from the Greek word “diaspeiro” which means “to scatter” or “to spread about.” In Ancient Greece, diaspora stated about people from prevailing countries who willingly

migrated to colonize conquered countries. In the present day, scholars distinguish two kinds of diaspora: forced and voluntary. Forced diaspora arises in case of emergency such as wars, or from natural disasters like famine or drought. As a result, the people belonging to such diaspora have feelings of loss, pain and finally want to return to their homeland. Whereas in case of voluntary diaspora here people tend to leave their homelands in search of job or a better livelihood, as observed in the late 17th century emigration of people to the United States from Europe. Unlike forced diaspora, voluntary groups, having cultural and spiritual relations to their country of origin, do not wish to return permanently. Instead, they develop a pride of their experience and feel socially and politically united. At present, the demands of enormous diaspora play an important role in manipulating the policies of the foreign governments in turn influencing their economy.

1.2 Indian Diaspora

The Global Migration Report 2020, mentions that India is the largest country with a strong diaspora of 17.5 million across the world, generating \$78.6 billion (around 3.4% of India's GDP) from Indians living overseas. Today, the Indian diaspora is flourishing more and creates an impact in the development of the nation. It contributes in various ways such as promoting the culture, **investment, lobbying and building a good reputation using their intelligence and industry.**

1.3 Significance of Indian Diaspora

1. Economic Front:

Indian diaspora represents quite a minority in various developed countries, which help to lobby keeping in view of India's interests. For example, Indians (approx. 2.8 million) occupy just 1% of U.S. population, but they are a highly educated richest minority, according to a report by Pew survey 2013.

2. Political Front:

Many Indian origin people hold crucial positions in many countries; in the United States they represent a significant part of Republicans and Democrats, as well as government posts.

3. Foreign Policy Front:

Indian diaspora has an impact on the political vote bank also. The community has considerable importance in matters related to foreign policy and associated government activities.

1.4 Challenges Faced by Indian Diaspora

1. Heterogeneous diaspora:

Indian Diaspora has different demands from various countries. The diaspora from Middle East countries want welfare issues. Whereas those from US look for greater investment opportunities. The communities residing at Fiji and Mauritius, have demands on cultural grounds.

2. Anti-Globalization:

The anti-globalization events led to increase in suspected hate crimes against the Indian community.

3. West Asian Crisis:

The fall in oil prices, have caused fears of a massive return of Indian nationals, creating an impact of demand on the job market.

4. Returning Diaspora:

Most workers going in West Asia are semi-skilled labours engaged in the infrastructure sector. After the boom in infrastructure ends India must be ready to utilise those workers returning home.

5. Negative Fallout:

Everything has a positive as well as negative side hence various separatist like the Khalistan movement work against Indian Interest.

2. Objectives

2.1. Highlighting the Growth Rate of Publications and Citations Analysis

2.2. Influential Authors, Institutions and their International Collaborations

2.3. Indicating highly sought after publications

2.4. Major Institutions known for their research output on this sub-domain

2.5. Key Subject area based on the same domain

2.6. Co-occurrence of highly used keywords

2.7. Principal funding areas in this research

3. Literature Search

Matsumoto, K & Britain, D. (2022) conducted a study on the rise of Japanese diaspora communities by their movements and demographic changes. It also includes culture, adaptation and educational institutions involvement of social organisations. They highlighted the socio-historical context of such diasporic Japanese communities worldwide. The current status of the community was taken under investigation in that paper.

Kumar, T.K. & Pillay, D.. (2021) focussed on the formation and movement of workers and migration of skilled professionals to the Gulf and West Asian countries. Indian diaspora is considered as the world's largest overseas groupings. They contribute a lot in the development of the country hence it becomes essential to study such overseas communities.

Kugiel, Patryk & Pedziwiatr, Konrad. (2021) piloted a study on the growth of Indian communities and their origin in Central European countries. They explored their impact on Indo-European relations and their future Indian relations in this region. Secondary sources such as statistical data, observations, interview and surveys were further conducted under this study.

4. Methodology

The data for the present study has been retrieved from the (WoS) Web of Science (<https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/solutions/web-of-science/>) repository, which is a highly acknowledged database for bibliometric studies worldwide. The search was conducted on 13/03/2022 using the keyword terms "Indian Diaspora" in combination with article title, abstract, and keywords. As a result of this search query, 218 records were retrieved from the database. The document type filters were applied.

Fig: Flowchart showing data extraction and filtration from WoS

A total of 217 articles were sorted for analysis. The data was exported from WoS in savedrecs.ciw file. The file was further screened using Zotero software and Plaintext formats with bibliographic details and indicators. The bibliographic information has been analyzed with MS-Excel, and Visualization of Similarities (VOS) viewer software (Van Eck and Waltman 2010).

5. Analysis and Interpretation

5.1. Growth Rate of Publications and Citations Analysis

The quantitative analysis of the research output (authors, years) helps understand the development of a particular field. A total of 217 research papers were published on Indian Diaspora from 1992 to 2021. These articles were written by 288 authors, published by 161 journals, and received 1641 total citations. The majority of the articles 213 were written in English, while 4 were reported in other languages. The year-wise growth rate of Indian Diaspora research, along with the citation score, publications count, and cumulative percentage, is shown in Table 1. The first paper in this area was published in 1992 indexed in the WoS database. During the period 1992 to 1996, only four articles were published in this area of research. The highest number of publications (N=17) occurred during 2019, while the highest number of 631 citations appeared in 2012-16. It reveals that both publication count and citation score have gradually increased. The recent year's publications got fewer citations than the previous period because of the time factor, and citations increase with time only.

Tab 1: year-wise growth rate of Indian Diaspora research

Year	TP	CTP	TC	TC/TP	TC/CTP	% Of TP	% Of CTP
1992-1996	4	4	85	21.25	21.25	1.84	1.84
1997-2001	12	16	84	7	5.25	5.52	7.37
2002-2006	22	38	271	12.31	1.86	10.13	17.51
2007-2011	63	101	384	6.09	3.80	29.03	46.54
2012-2016	48	149	631	13.14	4.23	22.11	68.66
2017-2021	68	217	186	2.73	0.85	31.33	100

TP=Total Publications; CTP= Cumulative Total Publications; TC=Total Citations

Fig: 1 Publications and citations

5.2. Authors and their Institutions

A total of 288 authors participated in the total research output (217 articles) on Indian Diaspora research during the period of study. The top 10 prolific authors and total publications, total citations, average citations per paper, and their affiliated institutes were identified and presented in table 2. The top 10 authors produced 22 papers and received 127 citations. Singh S from Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology was found the most productive author with 3 articles on this list. He got a TC of 21, ACCP of 7. As per the data, Vahed G (03), and others got a consecutive position in the list. Interestingly, Bhatia S from the Connecticut College, grabbed 3rd place in this list, but he has acquired only TC of 16 and ACCP of 8 for his 2 papers. Docquier F from the Luxembourg Inst Socioecon Res received the highest (29) citations for two papers and his average citations per paper (14.5) were entirely above other authors on the list. The comprehensive data of top prolific and influential authors are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Top 10 most productive and influential authors

Rank	Author	TP	TC	ACPP	Affiliation
1	Singh S	03	21	07	Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology
2	Vahed G	3	04	1.33	University of KwaZulu-Natal
3	Bhatia S	2	16	08	Connecticut College
4	Blell M	02	10	05	Newcastle University
5	Cabrall A	02	10	06	Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology
6	Chand M	02	08	04	Wichita State University
7	Madrigal L	02	12	06	University of South Florida
8	Dickinson J	02	09	4.5	University of Winchester
9	Docquier F	02	29	14.5	Luxembourg Inst Socioecon Res
10	Meers P	02	06	03	University of Antwerp

TP=Total Publications; TC=Total Citations; ACPP=Average Citations Per Paper

5.3. Top Ten Journals Titles Used for Publications

Journals are considered the primary source of light on research results and academic activities (Hu et al. 2019; Xie et al. 2020). The total research output, i.e., 217 papers, was published in 161 journals. Table 3 summarizes the top 10 journals with other indicators such as complete publications, citations, average citations per paper, publisher, and country. The top 10 journals have produced 44 articles (20.28%) of the total publications. The Journal *Man In India* was the most productive journal with 14 papers, 9 citations, 0.64 average citations per paper. Among the top journals, *Modern Asian Studies* was second most productive with 5 papers, followed by Contributions to Indian society (4), *Journal of commonwealth literature* (4) In this list, *Journal of ethnic and migration studies* of Routledge Journals, England, received the maximum of 47 total citations for its 3 papers and the highest average citations per paper (15.67).

Table 3: Top 10 most favored Journals

Rank	Journal	TP	TC	ACPP	Publisher	Country
1	Man In India	14	09	0.64	Serials Publications	India
2	Modern Asian Studies	5	15	3	Cambridge Univ Press	USA
3	Contributions to Indian society	4	19	4.75	Sage Publications	India
4	Journal of commonwealth literature	4	12	3	Sage Publications	England
5	Ariel a review of international English literature	3	0	0	Ariel Univ Calgary	Canada
6	Contemporary sociology – A journal of reviews	3	1	0.33	Sage Publications	USA
7	Continuum journal of media cultural studies	3	35	11.67	Routledge Journals	England
8	Journal of ethnic and migration studies	3	47	15.67	Routledge Journals	England
9	Journal of postcolonial writing	3	6	2	Routledge	England

					Journals	
10	Journal of royal anthropological institute	2	3	1.5	Wiley	USA

TP=Total Publications; TC=Total Citations; ACP=Average Citations per Paper

5.4. Leading Organizations Analysis

The data shows that the top 10 organizations have funded 47 (21.66 %) papers in the list of top funding organizations. As per the WoS data, the University Of Kwazulu Natal and University Of London has funded a maximum of 8 (3.69%) papers in the research domain on Indian Diaspora. At the same time, the University Of Hyderabad and Jawaharlal Nehru University got 4th and 5th place by providing funding to 9 research papers.

Table 3: Top 20 leading organizations

Rank	Organization	TP	% of 217	Region
1	University Of Kwazulu Natal	8	3.69	Durban
2	University Of London	8	3.69	London
3	California State University System	5	2.3	New York
4	University Of Hyderabad	5	2.3	Andhra Pradesh
5	Jawaharlal Nehru University	4	1.84	New Delhi
6	University Of Cape Town	4	1.84	Cape Town
7	University Of Illinois System	4	1.84	Chicago
8	Durham University	3	1.38	Durham
9	Harvard University	3	1.38	Boston
10	Macquarie University	3	1.38	Sydney

TP=Total Publications

5.5. Subject-wise Research area

Web of Science has its subject categories, and a single paper may fall into multiple subjects (Bapte & Gedam 2018). Therefore, several articles in different subject categories can be much more than actual 217 data considered for the study. As per the data, the total research output on Marxian political economy falls in 19 different WoS subject disciplines. The highest 21 articles were found in Anthropology. The comprehensive data of the top ten subject disciplines are shown in Table 6.

Table 4: Top 10 subject categories

Rank	Subject Categories	TP	% of 217
1	Anthropology	21	9.67
2	Area studies	20	9.21
3	History	20	9.21
4	Literature	19	8.75
5	Asian studies	18	8.29
6	Cultural studies	15	6.91
7	Sociology	14	6.45
8	Business economics	08	3.69
9	Communication	07	3.22
10	Geography	05	2.30

TP=Total Publications

5.6. Co-occurrence of Top 10 keywords

The analysis of keywords provides a description of research topics and emerging trends in a specific area. Table 8 displays the top 20 most frequently used author keywords, index keywords, and all keywords. There were 652, 451 and 255 keywords, author keywords, index keywords.

Table 4: Top 10 keywords

Rank	Keywords	Occurrence
1	Indian Diaspora	97
2	Diaspora	57
3	Migration	44
4	Identity	40
5	Geographies	36
6	Migrants	30
7	Gender	27
8	Immigration	25
9	Nationalism	23
10	Place	23

	Research	
7	Australian Council For International Agricultural Research	1
8	California State University Fullerton	1
9	chao Center For Asian Studies Rice University	1
10	Dept. Of Int'l Health At The Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School Of Public Health	1

TP=Total Publications

6. Discussion

India was earlier very subtle to talk on these issues because of the thought that it might offend the host countries, which are responsible for their welfare and security. Jawaharlal Nehru was of the view that Indian Diaspora could not expect India to fight for their rights as structured in India's Foreign Policy 1950. However Rajiv Gandhi during 1980 changed that view by including overseas Indian Diaspora in the development of the nation. Then again Vajpayee government after 2000 provided voting rights and NRI funds for citizens staying abroad. Further in 2015 the Ministry of External Affairs (MoE) launched the database for registration of overseas Indian citizens. The present government has launched "Know India Program" for engaging youth (18-30 yrs) with their Indian roots.

The study's findings highlight that the intellectuals are not concentrated in one or two universities or disciplines but are spread over vast universities and multidisciplinary fields. One weakness that the present research highlighted was the lack of international collaboration with researchers from developing countries. The majority of collaborative research by the Canadian Marxian political economists among the top 20 countries was with the United States and the United Kingdom. Here the academics are crucial for research in this field; they lack the financial resources to conduct their research. To get adequate funding for their research, they need to work a lot than those doing pro-system research. The study found that out of a total of 217 publications, from 1992 to 2021, only 11 publications were funded by the top 10 funding organizations. The merit of the researchers is that their methodology of analysis is critical. They try to enhance the consciousness about the various injustice and oppression in society. This is well reflected in their keywords which were dominated by the words such as migration, nationalism, identity, immigration, diaspora, etc.

Scholars must follow the same tact and techniques such as the impact factor publications, citations, etc. In order to attract young researchers and students to exercise and enroll in this type of research domain. In this context, the role of journals that challenge the mainstream intellectuals' discourse is quite crucial. Investigators have collaborated with the big publishing houses to enhance Diaspora research space in the last couple of decades. This is quite clear from the study's finding that renowned publishing houses publish the top 10 journals with substantial readership worldwide.

7. Conclusion

Indian diaspora can play an important role in unlocking India's potential. Hence the Indian government must formulate a NRI policy by working immediately with developed nations to return an appropriate percentage of tax revenue collected from the Indian diaspora. This can be debated by saying that these countries did nothing in creating such talents when these immigrants pay tax abroad. There is an immense need for creating a strategic diaspora evacuation policy in conflicting zones as it gives government very less time to act on such warnings. The diaspora can contribute in various key projects like Make In India, Clean Ganga, Swachh Bharat initiatives and so on. VAJRA (Visiting Advanced Joint Research Faculty) scheme was set up where various scientists, engineers, doctors, managers and top NRI professionals can lend their support to Indian public sector organization to work in the right direction. Ease of doing business can also help the diaspora related communities.

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